

ROLA PRAKTYKI PEDAGOGICZNEJ W KSZTAŁTOWANIU POZYCJI ZAWODOWEJ PRZYSZŁEGO NAUCZYCIELA SZKOŁY PODSTAWOWEJ

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Streszczenie. Zaktualizowano znaczenie priorytetowe uświadomienia przez przyszłych nauczycieli szkoły podstawowej roli praktyki pedagogicznej stosującej realizację zadań podwyżki jej stosowanej funkcjonalności w kształtowaniu fachowej pozycji pedagoga. Praktyka pedagogiczna rozpatruje się jako działalność edukacyjno-zawodowa, która łączy w sobie elementy nauczania i przygotowywania praktycznego, kształtowania myślenia zawodowo-pedagogicznego, ukierunkowania zawodowo-pedagogicznego, stosunku do fachu nauczyciela, twórczego samorozwoju studenta, które są podstawą pozycji zawodowej przyszłego nauczyciela. Nacisk kładziony jest na technologię „DoTREZ” (Experience - Tactics - Reflection - Application), której wykorzystanie przyczynia się do rozwoju umiejętności i umiejętności pedagogicznych poprzez zaangażowanie uczniów w różnego rodzaju praktyki pedagogiczne w celu stworzenia doświadczenia pedagogicznego jako podstawy do wdrożenia profesjonalnej pozycji przyszłego nauczyciela w działalności zawodowej. Określono składniki pozycji zawodowej przyszłego nauczyciela szkoły podstawowej – wartościowo-motywacyjny, kognitywno-intelektualny, refleksyjno-szacunkowy – ich pojęciowe wypełnienie podczas praktyki pedagogicznej. Odnotowano konieczność psychologiczno-pedagogicznego towarzyszenia przyszłego nauczyciela szkoły podstawowej jako jednolitego i bezustannego procesu studiowania i analizy działalności studenta-aplikanta, kształtowanie się i korygowanie jego oddzielnych jakości, zapewnienie fachowej pomocy na wszystkich etapach praktyki pedagogicznej. Uogólniono, że doskonałą właściwością psychologiczno-pedagogicznego towarzyszenia przyszłego nauczyciela szkoły podstawowej od tradycyjnego kierownictwa praktyką jest stworzenie umów do tolerancyjnego fachowego kontaktu na poziomie «subiekt – subiektnego» współdziałania. Ujawniono, że organizacja i przeprowadzenie praktyki pedagogicznej, która by sprzyjała kształtowaniu pozycji fachowej przyszłego nauczyciela szkoły podstawowej, spełniać należy do trzech etapów: przygotowawczy, kształtujący i refleksyjno-końcowy.

Etap kształtujący praktyki pedagogicznej podano przez konkretyzację faz (adaptacja przyszłego nauczyciela szkoły podstawowej do nowych umów fachowej działalności; aktywizacja fachowej działalności; twórcza kreacja własnego fachowo-pedagogicznego doświadczenia) i psychologiczno-pedagogicznego towarzyszenia. Zrobiono wniosek, że etap kształtujący praktyki pedagogicznej – to okres konsekwentnej zmiany sposobów spełnienia fachowo-pedagogicznej działalności przez przyszłych nauczycieli szkoły podstawowej: od wykonawcy - do reprodukcyjnego i dalej – do twórczej kreacji własnego doświadczenia, które potwierdza etap końcowy praktyki pedagogicznej.

Słowa kluczowe: przyszły nauczyciel, działalność edukacyjno-zawodowa, praktyka pedagogiczna, szkoła podstawowa, psychologiczno-pedagogiczne towarzyszenie, pozycja zawodowa, student-aplikant.

THE ROLE OF PEDAGOGICAL PRACTICE IN THE FORMATION OF THE PROFESSIONAL POSITION OF FUTURE TEACHER IN THE PRIMARY SCHOOL

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Abstract. The importance of understanding the future teachers of the elementary school about the role of pedagogical practice in fulfilling the tasks of increasing its applied functionalities in forming the professional position of the teacher is updated. Pedagogical practice is considered as educational-professional activity, which combines elements of training and practical training, formation of professional pedagogical thinking, professional-pedagogical orientation, value attitude to the teacher's profession, creative self-development of the student, which form the basis for the professional position of the future teacher-class teacher. The emphasis is on the technology of "ETRA" (Experience - Tactics - Reflection - Application), the use of which contributes to the development of pedagogical skills and skills through the involvement of students in various types of pedagogical practice in order to form a pedagogical experience as a basis for the professional position of the future teacher in professional activities. The components of the professional position of the future teacher of elementary school are determined - value-motivational, cognitive-intellectual, creative-activity, reflexivity and evaluation - their content content in the course of pedagogical practice. The necessity of psychological and pedagogical support of the future teacher of elementary school as a holistic and continuous process of studying and analyzing the activity of a student-practitioner, formation and correction of his individual qualities, provision of professional assistance at all stages of pedagogical practice is noted. It is generalized that the distinctive feature of the psychological and pedagogical support of the future teacher of elementary school from the traditional practice of practice is the creation of conditions for tolerant professional communication at the level of the "subject-subject" interaction. It was found out that the organization and conduct of pedagogical practice, which would contribute to the formation of the professional position of the future teacher of elementary school, should be carried out in three stages: preparatory, formative and reflexive and final. The formative stage of pedagogical practice is characterized through the specification of the stages (adaptation of the future teacher of the elementary school to the new conditions of professional activity, activation of professional activity, creative interpretation of own professional pedagogical experience) and psychological and pedagogical support. It is concluded that the formative stage of pedagogical practice is a period of consistent change of ways of carrying out professional and pedagogical activity by the future teacher of elementary

school: from performing - to reproductive and further - to creative interpretation of own experience, which testifies to the reflexive and final stage of pedagogical practice.

Keywords: future teacher, educational and professional activities, teaching practice, primary school, psychological and pedagogical support, professional attitude, student-trainee.

Introduction. Dynamic socio-cultural processes have led to the need for a critical reappraisal of traditional approaches to the training of future teachers, including primary school teachers, to their educational activities, and the essence of professional positions: from the specialist of the artist to a competent professional capable of responsible and creative professional activities, constantly striving for self-development and self-education, that is, to be an active subject of their own activities and to organize multivariate educational practices of students.

We draw attention to the fact that the very specificity of the direction of preparation 01 "Pedagogical Education" indicates that practical orientation should be provided by all levels of professional training of the future teacher: both theoretical training and practical training. In this case, pedagogical practice is foreseen at all educational and qualification levels, since the effectiveness of the professional training of future teachers, their further adaptation to professional activity depends to a great extent on its content, forms and methods. That is why the awareness of the future teachers of the elementary school of the role of pedagogical practice in fulfilling the tasks of increasing its applied functionalities in the formation of the teacher's professional position are of paramount importance today.

The purpose of the research: to analyze the role of pedagogical practice in shaping the professional position of the future teacher of elementary school at the stage of study at a higher education institution.

First of all, we note that it is pedagogical practice that increases self-realization of future teachers, mobilizes personal potential and reveals hidden capacities of a student. During pedagogical practice, students are able not only to observe (educational practice) in different forms and methods of pedagogical interaction, but also to try to carry out such activity on their own (industrial practice). It seems to us constructive that Y. Datsko (Datsko 2009, 199) suggests that pedagogical practice allows students to get acquainted with all aspects of future work intensively, to show a critical and meaningful attitude to the disciplines being studied in higher educational institutions, to include mechanisms of pedagogical reflection, to form the basis of professional self-esteem.

In line with what has been said, as is rightly noted by M. Dementiev (Dementyeva 2012, 138) (we agree with this statement), pedagogical practice cannot be considered as a professional activity, because it is a vocational and professional, because it combines elements of training and practical training, the formation of professional pedagogical thinking, vocational and pedagogical orientation, value attitude to the teacher's profession, and the student's creative self-development, which, in fact, form the basis of the professional position of the future teacher-class teacher.

In identifying effective approaches to constructing the pedagogical practice of future teachers, we consider it necessary to turn to the phenomenon of anthropic technologies, which, according to L. Redko's definition (Redko, 2007), are centered on the individual as the basic value and the social and spiritual essence of the person-figure. They constitute a structured synthesis of methods for organizing and conducting

discussions, seminars, discussions, training, mini-conferences, etc., taking into account the possibilities of visualizing these processes by technical or other means and the obligatory equality of all participants in these processes. And, therefore, it is quite legitimate to assert that their practical application effectively influences the formation of the professional position of the future teacher of elementary school, while ensuring the dialogue, creativity of the specified process.

In the context of the above-mentioned problem, the technology "ETRA" (Experience - Tactics - Reflection - Application) deserves attention as a kind of anthropic technologies, scientifically proved by L. Redko (Redko, 2007) and V. Khokhlova (Khokhlova, 2002), the essence of which is formation the experience of the practical activity of the individual through its phased implementation in the organization of interaction in small groups: the group receives a task and exchanges experience with the problem, collecting a kind of "bank of initial ideas"; correlating the problem with proposed ways of its solution; develops tactics (finds a way) for solving it and tries to make a decision in practice; At the reflexion stage, the group evaluates the result and the ways of its achievement, participation and personal contribution of each participant as a result of group interaction; at the application stage, an established strategy for using a successful model of interaction is worked out in order to solve a specific task and tasks that are identical to it, in real conditions of activity and (as needed) a pedagogical situation is played out.

It is precisely this kind of tactic that is useful for us, since the training of students for pedagogical practice and its direct implementation is a constant interaction in small groups, in particular, in systems "teacher-methodologist - students" - direct theoretical and methodical preparation for conducting pedagogical practice and "future teacher - students" - the process of teaching practice in real conditions. Obviously, the use of the technology "ETRA" promotes the development of pedagogical skills and skills through the involvement of students in various types of pedagogical practice in order to form a pedagogical experience as a basis for implementing the professional position of the future teacher of elementary school in professional activities. At the same time, there is an expansion and development of already existing previous experience, activation of self-development of professional activity and professional position of the future teacher, encouraging him to self-improvement.

Considering the development of the professional position of future teachers, we consider the algorithm for the implementation of the "ETRA" technology, proposed by L. Redko (Redko, 2007), and transformed by O. Litovka (Litovka, 2016, p.121-122), in relation to the formation of the experience of future teachers in developing a professional position.

- Stage I - acquaintance ("experience") - students, together with the methodologist, supervise the professional activity of experienced teachers at the stage of observational practice in the schools of the city; analyze types of professional pedagogical positions seen; compare them; in lessons on professionally oriented disciplines, they simulate fragments of lessons and pedagogical situations in which realized types of professional positions are realized, determine their advantages and disadvantages. Thus, the primary experience of the students is formed on ways of realizing a professional position in pedagogical activity, the process of self-determination and the choice of a student of a professional position of a certain type takes place.

- Phase II - Strategy (tactics) - students, together with a methodologist, develop a summary of the lesson (educational lesson) on the chosen subject and select such forms

and methods of conducting them, which would correspond to the peculiarities of realization by a student of a certain position's professional position.

- III stage - comprehension ("reflection") - after the lesson students evaluate the obtained result, the chosen tactics of its conduct, the degree of participation of each in the pedagogical interaction through self-examination, group analysis and comparison of the results make the appropriate conclusions. At this stage, we consider the use of reflexive technologies in order to ensure the permanent fixation by students-practitioners of the state of their professional development and self-development, professional behavior and position in this behavior. It is the use of reflexive techniques in shaping the pedagogical experience and the professional position of the future teacher of elementary school as the foundation of the educational process to determine effective interpersonal relationships in the systems of "teacher - student" and "teacher - student", will help to realize the student his professional "I".

- IV stage - practical-activity ("application") - if the tactics of the lesson (the approach to constructing a presentation of the content of the material, selected methods and methods of working with children, the form of conducting classes, the type of vocational pedagogical position, strategy of its implementation) proved to be effective for a specific educational subject for children of a certain age, the result is stored in the form of a lesson development in the general methodical treasury of the institution of higher education, so that students of other subgroups (in practice, students are often divided into subgroups) and groups could rely on the experience of their predecessors.

We draw attention to the fact that the bilateral nature of the process of formation of a professional position of the future teacher of elementary school in the course of pedagogical practice determines the presence of the formation of such components: value-motivation, cognitive-intellectual, creative-activity, reflexive and appraisal. It should be noted that among the components of a professional position there is an interconnection, interaction and interdependence. In this case, the value-motivational component carries out a system-specific function, determining the content and implementation of other components, which, in turn, is a means and condition for the formation and development of elements of the value-motivational component, as well as the overall professional position of the future teacher of the elementary school.

Formation of value-motivational component of a professional position takes place taking into account the following grounds:

- Emergence of the need for continuing vocational education, the development of a future teacher of primary classes of sustainable motivation to professional activity;

- Formation of value orientations of the future teacher of elementary school, acceptance of values of pedagogical activity as personal in the process of preparation for professional self-realization and realization of own professional position in pedagogical activity, awareness of the highest value of pedagogical activity - student;

- Formation of a future teacher of an elementary class attitude towards himself as a subject of his own life;

- Development of the future teacher-classroom of tolerance to the surrounding reality.

The formation of the cognitive-intellectual component of the professional position of the future teacher of elementary school, which accumulates the totality of theoretical and methodological knowledge, professional knowledge, the ability to independently obtain and critically understand the necessary information; erudition and competence, is

determined by the following laws:

- Correlation of theoretical knowledge with practice;
- Enriching and deepening the knowledge of the future teacher about modern school, peculiarities of the course of the educational process at the present stage of development of the education system;
- Development of the desire to know new or to improve already existing;
- Organization of research and experimental work of the future teacher of elementary school in the field of education.

The formation of the creative and active component of the professional position of the future teacher of elementary school is conditioned by the following laws:

- Development of a future teacher of elementary classes of professionally meaningful skills (analytical, designing, constructive, organizational and communicative skills of social interaction), skills of creative, research approach to professional activity;
- Development of initiative, independence of thinking of the future teacher of elementary school, creative perception of pedagogical activity, ability to optimally build pedagogical communication with subjects in the field of elementary education.

Reflective and evaluation component of the professional position of the future teacher of elementary school is formed with the following components:

- Improvement of the skills of performing the basic types of professional activity by the future teacher of elementary school in diagnostics, goal determination, planning, organization, implementation, evaluation of educational process;
- Formation of methods of adequate self-examination and self-assessment of the future teacher of elementary classes in the process of fulfilling their basic functions, the formation of self-realization skills in pedagogical activity.

There is an opinion (Dementiev 2012, 139) that the formation of a professional position of the future teacher of elementary school in the course of pedagogical practice is largely correlated with the way student leadership is directed by teachers. We are in agreement with the statement of the scientist that the main function of the leaders of pedagogical practice should be psychological and pedagogical support of the future teacher-class teacher. In the context of the study, we consider it necessary to make some clarifications on the interpretation of the concept of "psychological and pedagogical support".

First of all, we note that in the reference editions (Great Dictionary of Contemporary Ukrainian Language, 2001) the concept of "accompaniment" is interpreted as an action with the meaning of "go next", as well as its multidimensionality, in particular, as: actions with the meaning of accompany, accompany; something that accompanies a certain action, a phenomenon; combination of action with another, by-effects; adding something to something, supplementing something (Goncharenko, 1997).

Concerning the notion of "action" as the key dominant, it is interpreted as "work, activity, the accomplishment of something, a set of actions," "intentionally mediated activity, aimed at achieving an informed goal." Actions -relatively independent processes, regardless of what they are - external, practical, internal or mental. Unlike its own activities, the action has no independent motive, but is subject to the activity, the content of which it forms (Encyclopedia of practical psychology).

In defining the concept of "psychological and pedagogical support," we were served by the definition of "psychological support" borrowed from E. Zeeer (E. Zero 2003) and concretized it in the context of the outlined problem. Thus, under the

psychological and pedagogical support of the future teacher of elementary school, we mean a holistic and continuous process of studying and analyzing the activity of a student-practitioner, establishing and correcting his individual qualities, providing future teacher with professional assistance at all stages of pedagogical practice. At the same time, the distinctive feature of the psychological and pedagogical support of the future teacher of elementary school from the traditional leadership practice is the creation of conditions for tolerant professional communication at the level of "subject-subject" interaction by:

- transfer of the goals and objectives of future activities to the goals and objectives of the future teacher of elementary school as a subject of professional activity;
- compliance of teachers of higher education institutions and basic educational institutions with the practice of uniform requirements for future class teachers, taking into account their personal characteristics and objective circumstances; carrying out a step-by-step analysis of the course and results of the activity of the future teacher of elementary school by all organizers of pedagogical practice;
- integration of the activities of all participants in the practice of psychological and pedagogical support of the future teacher of elementary school in the course of his professional development, the formation of a professional position.

We draw attention to the fact that the organization and conduct of pedagogical practices that would contribute to the formation of the professional position of the future teacher of elementary school, it is advisable to carry out in three stages: preparatory, forming and reflexive and final. In particular, the preparatory stage is carried out during theoretical training of students at lectures, practical classes, etc. The formative stage is implemented directly in the course of practice and includes the following stages:

- Adaptation of the future teacher of elementary school to the new conditions of professional activity;
- activation of professional activity;
- creative interpretation of own professional and pedagogical experience.

The reflexive and final stage takes place both during the practice and after its completion.

It is essential that the organization of pedagogical practice is carried out in a cyclic sequence of all stages of the educational and professional activity of the future teacher of elementary school, and most importantly, in the complicated trajectory. In this case, organizational and pedagogical conditions of pedagogical practice should include:

- diagnostic conditions (lively discussion, as well as discussion in the Internet space of contradictions and difficulties in the professional-pedagogical activity of students-practitioners of the last year of study, the selection of the corresponding types, their characteristics);
- designing conditions (development of goals, tasks of pedagogy focused on forming the main competencies of the teacher, their scientific substantiation, preparation of bases of pedagogy, elaboration of criteria of project effectiveness and conditions of implementation in practice);
- the conditions for professional self-education (ensuring the real professional growth of students through the development of individualized methods, techniques and means of self-education as a form of self-improvement of the teacher, participation in student scientific and practical conferences, etc.);
- conditions of value-semantic attitude towards the future profession (interaction

with mentors, students, execution of assignments, solving pedagogical tasks, etc.) (Gabdrakhmanova, 2015).

In the context of the problem under consideration, it is necessary to describe in more detail the forming stage of pedagogical practice through the specification of the identified stages. The stage of adaptation of the future teacher of elementary school to the new conditions of professional activity is understood by us as a period of active assimilation by students of the system of roles and methods of pedagogical activity in the new conditions. At the same time, the main problem that is solved in the process of adaptation is the approach of the goal and value orientations of the school and the student-trainee, assimilation of the norms of behavior, established traditions, finding their place and role in the changing professional-pedagogical environment.

Note that at this stage, the future teacher of elementary school is accustomed to the rhythm of the pedagogical process of the school and the children, begins to navigate the system of internally school relationships and relationships. He develops the ability of subjective goal-setting (goal definition) by comparing his own goals, his own activities with other subjects: pupils, teachers of the school and institution of higher education. The meaning of psychological and pedagogical support at the stage of adaptation of the future teacher of elementary school to the new conditions of professional activity is to provide him with assistance in removing anxiety, in mobilizing professional activity through counseling, training for self-regulation, etc. Thus, successful adaptation of the future teacher of primary classes to the new conditions allows him, in our opinion, to begin active pursuit of his own professional activities.

The stage of activating the professional activity of the future teacher of elementary school is a period of active professional self-determination and development of students, the formation of a professional position, values-semantic landmarks for professional pedagogical activities, realistic goals and programs for its implementation. At this stage, psychological and pedagogical support is provided by ensuring the coordination of the actions of the future teacher of elementary school and teachers of an educational institution, ensuring the unity of the requirements of the teachers of the school and institution of higher education, providing advisory assistance. At the same time, the effectiveness of educational activities is determined by the complex application of the future teacher of elementary classes of knowledge in psychological and pedagogical disciplines and disciplines of subject preparation, knowledge of age and individual characteristics of students, interests and inclinations, relationships in the student's team, as well as knowledge and skills to apply in practice methods and techniques individual and differentiated education and upbringing of junior pupils.

The stage of creative interpretation of the own experience of a future teacher of elementary school is a period of creative transformation by a student-practitioner of his own activities, the acquisition of subjective meaningful creative experience, the formation of his independent thinking, which, in our opinion, is not limited to specific terms. In the process of pedagogical practice, the creative interpretation of own experience takes place in different directions of the activity of the future teacher of elementary school and is expressed in his desire to choose non-traditional forms and methods of teaching and education; in readiness to use modern high-tech teaching aids, in an effort to carry out research and experimental work; implement the obtained results into practical activities, etc. The psychological and pedagogical support of the future teacher of elementary school at this stage is to mobilize the creative activity of a student-

student through counseling, forming their own interest in the results of creative activity.

Thus, it is quite legitimate to assert through the prism that the formation stage of pedagogical practice is a period of a consistent change in the ways of carrying out the professional and pedagogical activity of the future teacher of the elementary school: from the executive to the reproductive and then to the creative interpretation of his own experience, which confirms the reflexive and final stage pedagogical practice. The psychological and pedagogical support of the final stage thus acquires the character of cooperation and takes place on the basis of open dialogue, based on the trust of the future teacher of the elementary school, respect for his personality. In this approach, the student-practitioner forms an adequate attitude to practice, and a sense of significance in the team is strengthened.

The key role in the professional self-determination of future teachers of elementary school, the formation of their professional position is played by the production practice provided by the curriculum of the educational qualification level "Bachelor" (specialty 013 "Primary education"), as it provides personally oriented, integrated, continuous and creative character of training teacher-teacher through the possibilities of developing professional freedom, the initiative of practitioners, their responsibility for their own subjectivity. In our opinion, the best opportunities in this regard are, in particular, educational and educational practice at the school, according to the tasks which in its content provides for in-depth study of the students' educational and educational work of the school and conducting of their psychological and pedagogical research in the framework of experimental training (realization on the lessons of cognitive-educational tasks, taking into account the specifics of individual subjects, the age of students, their actual educational capacity, observation of mental activity of junior pupils, self-assessment self-esteem, interpersonal relationships in a group of students, etc.), which simultaneously confirms the dynamics of qualitative characteristics of the person's and professional development of the future teacher (vocational and pedagogical orientation of interests and needs of students-practitioners, knowledge of the basic specificity of professional-pedagogical activity, reflexive position, etc.) (Prima, 2009, p.176-177).

In this case, a student-student, as noted by I. Budnaruk (Bodnaruk, 2006, p.7), speaks in various functional positions: the organizer of the educational activities of students and the organizer of his own activities, the content of which is a special subject of awareness, analysis and evaluation. In our opinion, the value of the practice is that the student acquires experience in implementing a holistic educational process in the context of real professional activities (taking into account the specifics of the educational program).

Conclusions. Thus, summarizing the above, we note that pedagogical practice as a whole is a dominant component of the formation of a professional position of a future teacher of elementary school at the stage of study at an institution of higher education, when "fundamental knowledge is applied and understood, the development of pedagogical thinking, creative abilities of students is intensified, opportunities are created for the self-actualization of the student, the comprehensive identification of his personality, personal self-realization, professional self-determination as a condition of dynamic and continuous improvement of the future teacher"(Prima, 2009, p.179).

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